

Investigation of *Croton caudatus* Geisel – Isolation of Stigmastan-3,6-dione,5 α

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CROTON caudatus Geisel (Fam.: Euphorbiaceae; collected in Darjeeling) is a medium-sized plant growing profusely in the Eastern Himalayan range at an altitude of about 6000 ft. The leaves are odorous and find extensive application in relieving pain from sprains¹. Among the local people of Darjeeling, this plant is popular for its use in the treatment of stomach disorders. Its extracts have been found to possess some insecticidal and insect-repelling properties. Previous examination of the plant led to the isolation of three triterpenoids, viz. taraxerone, taraxerol and taraxeryl acetate besides sitosterol and two rearranged labdane type norditerpene, viz. teucvidin and croto-caudin from this plant². The present reinvestigation on the stem-bark of this plant led to the isolation of a compound belonging to a rare class of nortriterpenoids, viz. stigmastan-3,6-dione,5 α (1) in addition to taraxerone, taraxerol, sitosterol and an unidentified compound (5% methanolic chloroform, M^+ 412), m.p. 205°.

The concentrated petrol (b.p. 60–80°) extract of the dried and powdered stem-bark of *Croton caudatus* when chromatographed over silica gel yielded taraxerone (2), C₃₀H₄₈O (M^+ 424), m.p. 238°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1700 cm⁻¹; m/z 424 (M^+), 409 (M^+ -CH₃), and taraxerol (3), C₃₀H₅₀O (M^+ 426), m.p. 278°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3480 cm⁻¹; m/z 426 (M^+), 411 (M^+ -CH₃), 393 (M^+ -CH₃-H₂O) in the petrol-benzene (1:1) eluates, and sitosterol, m.p. 137° in the benzene eluates. These three compounds were identified by direct comparison (m.p., m.m.p., co-tlc in several systems, superimposable ir and ¹H nmr spectra) with the authentic samples.

Repeated fractional crystallisation of the solid, obtained from the benzene eluate in later fractions afforded a white crystalline solid, m.p. 195°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1710 cm⁻¹, which gave a pale green coloration with the Liebermann-Bürchardt reagent, showing its steroidal/terpenoidal nature and no colour with TNM for a double bond. The 70 eV high-resolution mass spectra showed a molecular

ion peak at m/z 428.366211 (diff. 0.7629 amu from calculated) corresponding to molecular formula C₂₉H₄₈O₂. Its fragmentation pattern suggested that it had the stigmastane skeleton, with the sequential loss of methylene groups from the molecular ion followed by peaks at m/z 287 (M^+ -C₁₀H₂₁) and 245 (M^+ -C₁₀H₂₁-42)³ suggesting the possible identity of the compound with stigmastan-3,6-dione,5 α (1) which has been supported by a detailed 200 MHz ¹H nmr analysis of compound 1 whose assignments are given here: 200 MHz ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 0.70 (3H, s, C₁₈ protons), 0.85–0.95 (9H, m, C₂₆, C₂₇ and C₂₉ protons), 0.93 (3H, d, J 6.4 Hz, C₂₁ protons), 0.97 (3H, s, C₁₉ protons), 1.26 (16H, brs, C₁, C₁₁, C₁₂, C₁₅, C₁₆, C₂₂, C₂₃ and C₂₈ protons), 1.48–2.12 (7H, m, C₈, C₉, C₁₄, C₁₇, C₂₀, C₂₄ and C₂₅ protons), 2.07–2.37 (5H, m, C₂, C₄ and C₅ protons), 2.57 (2H, C₇ protons-AB system).

Stigmastan-3,6-dione,5 α was first isolated by Hayashi *et al.*⁴ from *Metasequoia glyptostroboides* Hu et Cheng, and subsequently from other sources, viz. *Macranga tanarius*⁵, *Aristolochia* species⁷ and *Boehmeria platyphylla*⁸. This rare compound has been isolated for the first time from the genus *Croton*.

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Potentiometric and Visual Determination of Potassium using Periodate as Reagent

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THE literature survey reveals that the titrimetric methods for the determination of potassium suffer from many disadvantages like using costly

chemicals like chloroplatinic acid and silver nitrate¹ or involving a large number of operations and time consuming, complex nature and lack of accuracy^{2,3}. The earlier reports on the determination of potassium as cobaltinitrite are of contradictory nature⁴⁻⁷.

The present method of determination of potassium as periodate has a number of advantages like high molecular weight and determining by a volumetric method.

Experimental

A Elico LI-120 digital potentiometer along with platinum and saturated calomel electrodes was used for potential measurements. The titration mixture was stirred by means of a magnetic stirrer.

A 0.05 *N* solutions of iron(II) ammonium sulphate, tin(II) chloride and titanium(III) chloride were prepared and standardised⁸⁻¹⁰. 0.1% solutions of the above mentioned indicators except starch were prepared in distilled water. A 1% solution of starch was prepared. All the reagents used are of AnalaR grade.

Procedure. Precipitation of potassium as periodate: The sample solution containing 15–45 mg of potassium was evaporated to dryness and mixed with concentrated nitric acid (5 ml) and evaporated again. After cooling, 20% periodic acid solution (5 ml) and aldehyde-free ethanol (5 ml) were added and mixed well. The mixture was cooled to 0° for ~2 h and the precipitate was then filtered, dried and dissolved in water to titrate with iron(II), tin(II) and titanium(III) solutions.

For fertiliser samples the above procedure was followed after expelling ammonia (if present) at 100° on boiling-water-bath.

Titration of potassium periodate: Potassium periodate solution (5–10 ml) and a required volume of phosphoric acid or hydrochloric acid to maintain 9–12 or 2–5 *M* acidity, respectively in a total volume of 50 ml were taken followed by the addition of dye indicator (0.2 ml) or starch (1 ml). The mixture was then titrated with the reductant solution in carbon dioxide atmosphere to a sharp colour change of the indicator. Alternatively, the indicator solution was excluded and titrated potentiometrically to a sharp break in the potential.

Results and Discussion

By separate experiments, it is observed that the reaction is quantitative in 9–12 *M* phosphoric acid with iron(II) and in 2–5 *M* hydrochloric acid media with tin(II) or titanium(III). Starch indicator is not applicable in the visual determination of

potassium periodate with iron(II) as reductant. The potentials are stabilised immediately after the addition of the reductant throughout the titration. A potential break of about 240 mV for iron(II), 250 mV for tin(II) and 210 mV for titanium(III) is observed for 0.04 ml of 0.05 *N* reductant solution.

The cooling of the solution to 0° reduces the common ion effect of the excess periodate present as indicated by Crouthamel¹¹.

The colour change of all the indicators is from blue to colourless. But when starch is used as indicator for titanium(III), the colour change is from colourless to blue. An indicator correction of 0.02 ml is observed when 0.01 *N* reductant solutions are used for 0.2 ml of 0.1% dye solution. Whereas the correction is negligible when 0.05 *N* reductant solutions is used. As the reaction between titanium(III) and the dye indicators used is found to be slow, 5 ml of 0.1 *M* sodium oxalate solution is added to catalyse the reaction.

The periodate (I⁷⁺ stage) is reduced to iodide (I⁻¹ stage) (where 8-electron change is observed) with iron(II) or tin(II) and the periodate is reduced to ICl (I⁺¹ stage) (where 6-electron change is observed) with titanium(III).

The potassium content in KCl, K₂SO₄, KNO₃, murite of potash and N.P.K. fertilisers is estimated with an average error of below 0.5%.

Interferences: Chloride and phosphate do not interfere but sulphate interferes if present at any concentration. Hence sulphate has to be precipitated with barium chloride in those samples.

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